

ABOUT THE QUALITY OF EDUCATIONAL ELECTRONIC RESOURCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10036657>

***Abstract.** This article discusses the issues of about the quality of educational electronic resources.*

***Keywords:** information technology, information resources, the quality of EER.*

An analysis of the existing practice of using EER shows that the most active implementation of EER is observed in the practical part of the lesson. This is explained by the large amount of routine work of the teacher in creating and checking individual practical tasks, which creates the need to automate such activities; and also, because learning is significantly individualized [1,2,3].

However, EERs are rarely used in the process of studying theoretical material in the classroom. Despite the obvious pedagogical advantages, the use of EER is still difficult for certain reasons: the lack of preparation of teachers to use EER for teaching theoretical knowledge, the small number of EER suitable for effective systematic use in the educational process, the low quality of existing EER. Speaking about the quality of EER, it should be noted that the quality of EER is understood as a set of properties (characteristics) of EER that determine its suitability for use in the educational process [4].

Modern educational activities provide the student with the opportunity to study theory, conduct experimental research, acquire practical skills and abilities through training actions, and exercise self-control at a convenient individual pace. The same EER can be used in the theoretical and practical parts of the lesson, for organizing independent learning of a training topic, or during current and final control [5].

The spread of electronic learning tools, classified as EER, reduces the interest of the education sector in the development of service tools, since programs that facilitate routine calculations, processing experimental data, and similar programs have become common tools in recent years. As a rule, all existing EERs include service modules necessary for their operation [6].

Educational software tools aimed at monitoring and testing the level of knowledge of students, as well as EERs containing such tools, are becoming more widespread. They significantly relieve teachers from the routine work of creating multivariate individual practical tasks and monitoring their implementation. The opportunity to frequently monitor knowledge increases motivation to learn.

The constantly growing scale of development and implementation of new educational electronic resources in the field of education has necessitated the need to ensure the high quality of these new and expensive products at the stages of design, development, testing and implementation. The deep relationship between the quality of developed EERs and the quality of the technology for their creation and the cost of resources for development is especially important when it is necessary to obtain a final product with high quality indicators. In recent years, this has led to a significant change in the methodology for creating and improving computer tools aimed at intensifying learning. Increased requirements for the quality of such products have led to a desire to take into account regulated technologies and existing international standards.

In substantive and methodological terms, the quality of EER can to a large extent be ensured and controlled by traditional methods based on determining the compliance of the existing regulatory documents in the system of the Ministry of Education (state standards, standard curricula, work programs, etc.), within the framework of the activities of the expert council of the Ministry education, educational and methodological associations, councils, etc.

More complex is the problem of ensuring high quality EER as a means of information technology, which must be solved in accordance with the requirements of International standards and agreements, legislation.

REFERENCES

1. Швецкий М.В. Методическая система фундаментальной подготовки будущих учителей информатики в педагогическом вузе в условиях двухступенчатого образования: Автореферат дисс... д-ра пед. наук. - СПб., - 1994. - 36 с.
2. Чванова М.С. Информационные технологии в обучении: Учеб, пособие. - Тамбов: ТППУ. - 1997. - 121 с.
3. Человеческий фактор. Сб., под редакцией Г. Салвенди, в 6-ти томах, - М.: Мир. - 1991.
4. Akramova, L., & Rustamova, N. (2023, June). Computer-human interaction: Visualization of the educational process as a means of increasing the efficiency of the education. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
5. Rustamova, N. (2023, June). The interaction of vitagenic experience, computer and a human in a smart system. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.